

DESIGN CONCEPT OF SMC COMPRESSION MOULDING
TO PREVENT A FAULT CAUSED BY FLOW STATE

Tsuneo Hirai

Department of Mechanical Engineering,
Doshisha University,
Kyoto 602
Japan

ABSTRACT

When composite materials are used in compression moulding process, problems can arise due to the heterogeneity of materials, caused by fibre orientation during flow. To overcome the faults in practice occurring during the process, it is necessary to investigate the flow characteristics during unsteady forming process. The paper gives a review of investigation made at Doshisha University into flow characteristics of composite materials, and the application to a particular mould configuration to preventing the faults for dealing with fibre composite materials.

INTRODUCTION

As the utilization of composite materials widens, the demands for mass production of the materials are increased, and fibre composite prepreg materials should be achieved still greater prominence in the form of sheet moulding compounds. When composite materials are used in compression moulding process problems arise due to the heterogeneity of materials, caused by fibre orientation during flow. In practice the following faults might be observed in moulded products : a) Surface sink, where surface cavities are produced on convex face during the final stages of moulding. b) Weld line initialing cracks at the line which are created in regions between converging flows where the fibre direction becomes normal to the surface. c) Brittle region, which occur at the ends of fins due to stress concentration in the resin-rich parts.

d) Irregularity of fibre volume fraction in the product with a rib part caused by an asymmetrical flow pattern. e) Warp, that is out-of-plane displacement by residual stresses, might be caused by imbalance in temperature distribution in the product at the final stage of the process.

To overcome the problems occurring during the process, by improvement in mould design and forming conditions, it should be necessary to investigate the flow characteristics of the materials during unsteady forming process. Vigorous R & D effort aimed at resolving above problems is now under way at automobile manufacturers around the world. When ribs are used, sink marks are apt to occur on the panel surface, which markedly degrade the surface accuracy and involved great risks of weld line in the case of wide rib part.

RHEOLOGY OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS IN COMPRESSION MOULDING

Composite prepreg materials are essentially heterogeneous structure and moulding them results in unstable deformation. The flow state during a press forming process can be analysed by representing the material flow as being unsteady. For an unstable condition, a Lagrangean description should be applied, but to simplify the analysis the progressive step by formulation method is developed using an Eulerian description [1-2]. The method is employed to simulate the mechanical behaviour of the composite during the unsteady moulding process.

The modelling the mechanical behaviour during deformation is achieved as shown in Fig.1. For the first step, the deformation state does not depend on the compression rate of the punch, but is governed by eigenmode of deformation state before initiation of flow is calculated by eigenvalue analysis. The first mode should be used to investigate the subsequent process, because the energy level of first mode is lower than next. The sequence of deformation is then simulated by linear incremental analysis, as an infinitesimal deformation due to punch pressure.

The practical case of forming a T-shaped component from a flat blank, in a closed die has been studied as the fundamental case of mechanical behaviour. Then problems encountered in practice include centralplane weakness, thermal gradients in the formed component at the ejection stage and nonsymmetric flow behaviour as will be seen later. These aspects have been investigated analytically using finite element formulations, and verified by experimental results.

Fig.1 Flow chart for numerical procedure and their problems.

It is assumed that the composite has orthogonal anisotropic properties depend on the orientation of the reinforcement. The first mode obtained by eigenvalue analysis indicates asymmetrically that the nodal points shift not only in vertical direction, but also horizontally, immediately on loading. Secondly, the linear incremental deformation theory is used to calculate the progressive deformation state. The dots shown in Fig.2 indicate where the reaction force at nodal points on the punch surface change from compression to tension in

Fig.2 Deformation state obtained by linear incremental analysis.

the case of T-shaped flow canal with a free boundary over the rib cavity shown by C-D in the figure. The phenomenon indicates the possibility of micro-buckling in lamina at the surface. The asymmetrical appearance of dotted nodal point confirms the tendency for snaking of the weld line about the symmetrical axis and experimental result shows the aspect of weld line configuration. From the result of the above microscopic analysis, the strain rate is determined and the initial viscosity can be estimated.

The flow state of composite materials cannot be expressed by type of flow equation used for a convenient materials, since they are not isotropic materials but include fibrous reinforcement. Therefore, on the assumption that with composite materials the fibre orientation yields different flow resistance in directions normal and parallel to the flow, the homogeneous orthotropic pseudo-plastic equations are derived and used as governing equations to analyse the flow state. It is also assumed that a fibre orientates along a stream line when the extrusion ratio is greater than unity. The pseudo-plastic viscosity K_j ($j=L,T$), in parallel and normal directions to flow, are transformed into K_i ($i=x,y$) by transformation matrix. Consequently the governing equation can be written by considering the negligible terms as shown in Fig.1, where the invariant $J_2=e_{ij}*e_{ij}$. The method of weighted residual(a Galerkin formulation)is used to solve equations.

In order to determine the flow characteristics of the composite, the ratio of the pseudo-plastic viscosity K_T/K_L is assumed as 3, since this case indicates an anisotropic flow resistance. The pattern of initial velocity vectors, including the effect of initial viscosity obtained by linear incremental analysis, is shown in Fig.3. The flow pattern is asymmetric about the axis and suggests a tendency for disturbance of flow in successive steps. Numerical results for the flow states during moulding at constant room temperature are shown in Fig.4, as an example of unsteady flow using also the progressive step by step method.

Fig.3 Initial velocity vectors for initial viscosity obtained from incremental analysis.

In the figures it is evident that the flow swings around the rib corner, and has a tendency to incline upward over the horizontal die face as shown by ringed vectors. The flow state suggests that there is a resin-rich region in the product. To prevent or minimise a fault in the product the following methods could be able to be considered. In a commercial operation the die is pre-heated in order to minimise the moulding cycle time. This creates the thermal diffusion and temperature distribution in the materials. An example of the influence of thermal diffusion on the flow state is indicated for temperature distribution and corresponding flow state, respectively, with alternate application of thermal diffusion analysis and flow analysis (1). The tendency for fibres to move slightly upward during horizontal displacement, as shown by ringed vectors in Fig.4, is reduced under the conditions developing without resin-rich part formation.

Fig.4 Flow states.

PREDICTION OF ASYMMETRIC FLOW PATTERN AND FILLING FLOW OF MATRIX IN FINAL STAGE

To apply the anisotropic characteristics to composite prepreg material it is necessary to determine the the effect of variations of anisotropic stiffness ratio (EL/ET) and anisotropic flow resistance (KT/KL). The first mode shape and the subsequent deformation states obtained by eigenvalue and linear incremental analysis respectively for different anisotropic stiffness ratio EL/ET indicate a similar mode. The occurrence of the pressure-free nodal points on the punch surface at progressive stage of deformation are shown in Fig.5. With increase in anisotropy the extent of the pressure free surface, and the likelihood of micro-buckling at the surface, is seen to be greater, particularly in the later stages of compression. The actual development of the buckling depends on the length of fibres and the extent of the pressure free surface.

Fig.5 Pressure-free nodes during deformation.

Fig.6 Velocity vectors in the case of anisotropic resistance.

The velocity vector distribution at some step of progressive step by step method are indicated in Fig.6. A fairly uniform flow is evident for the isotropic case ($KT/KL=1$) but for anisotropic conditions the velocities increase toward the center of the channel. Surface sink, that is, sink mark might be produced during the final stage of moulding in being filled up a vacant space by the material after the flow front reaches the lower mould. Since the velocities distribution increasing towards the centre in the rib part as the figure indicates the extrusion ratio is less smaller than unity in the remainder canal configuration, the fibre orientation might rotate parallel way to at the vacant

Fig.7 Orientation of reinforcement after front flow reached at the mould.

boundary. Then the organization of reinforcement shall be prevent from flowing in order to rapid increasing of pressure in the laminated part as see later. Material construction in the case being installed by the final orientated fibres is show in Fig.7 after the flow analysis. The subsequent deformation states obtained by incremental analysis, replacing the stiffness drops caused by occurrence of microscopic distortions with a problem including material non-linearity and geometrical non-linear displacement are shown in Fig.8 in being indicated stress free nodal points. Surface sink might occur in the domain by the stress state. Fig.9 suggests sudden increasing of loading pressure yields under a condition of spherical stress tensor in the laminated plane part by considering a negative value of the equivalent stress and strain. The

Fig.8 Initiation of stress free nodal points in punch surface upon rib part.

Fig.9 Stress state of elastic region illustrated by elements in black. condition is verified by the experimental result shown by line I in Fig.10 [4]. The line II and III in the figure indicate the two times pressure drops, and the first one is caused by the initial surface sink dependent on a risk of weld line and the second on a developing of sink

Fig.10 Mechanical behaviour indicated by variation of working pressure during the process.

(a) Flow states.

(b) Flow states in rib part. (c) Flow vector distribution.

Fig.11 Flow state and distribution of flow velocities.

mark on the modelling on flowing the penetrated resin through the fibre construction. The application of anisotropic flow resistance is how and why event occur. Therefore the value of resistance in the laminated plate part is indicated very high but low in the rib canal caused by the

circumstance of pressure. Flow resistance at the inlet portion to rib reasonable values dependent on the fibre orientation at the part. The flow state and the distribution of flow velocity are shown in Fig.11. The tendency of surface sink is suggested by the figures and the similar state on sink marks are indicated by the measurement of panel surface.

METHOD OF MINIMISING SINK MARKS AND TO PREVENT WELD LINE FORMATION

Surface sink, that is, sink mark might be produced during the final stage of moulding and depends on an aspect ratio of the fibre in connection with the thickness of rib confining smaller value for its application to practical affairs to take away the mark. Since the swing the velocity vectors in the upper region of the rib is greater with increase in anisotropy factor suggested above, the flow state of fibre is limited on the way of narrow rib canal. In the case a stiffness and strength might decrease compare with composites without such a resin rich-part. To prevent the product with rib parts from the initiation of surface sink caused by stress free boundary at the rib canal, it is developed by

Fig.12 Configuration of mould with counter punch.

(a) With back pressure.

(b) Without back pressure.

Photo.1 Configuration of flow state.

the method on the die design installed with a counter punch moving downward in proportion to pouch stroke owing to decreasing of back pressure. The design configuration is shown in Fig.12 and moulded states are observed by the Photo.1. The results suggest an effective way of preventing weld line in the initial stage and sink mark in the final stage as the resin penetrate already into a vacant space at the beginning of process. There is a final remark on a practical application which is quite encouraging. Another way is obtained by hybrid lamination of prepreg materials having various stiffness [5].

CONCLUSION

The progressive flow state of composites during the compression moulding process has been analysed numerically by assuming the flow to be anisotropic. The numerical results obtained by the Progressive Step by Step Method in this paper are shown to be in good agreement with experiment. Numerical results on the mechanical behaviour during the moulding process suggest the problems caused by fault in product and their preventing methods. The methods being developed in this paper give an application to practical affairs.

REFERENCES

- 1) Hirai,T., Rheology of Carbon Fibre Composite Prepreg Materials. In Development in Reinforced Plastics-5, ed.G.Pritchard, Elsevier Applied Science Publishers Ltd., London, 1986, pp.233-65.
- 2) Hirai,T., Advanced Technology of Plasticity, 1, 1984, pp.13-18.
- 3) Hirai,T. and Semba,T., Composite Materials, Proc. of Japan-U.S Conference, 1981, pp.410-17
- 4) Yamabe,M., Fujiwara,T., Hirai,T. and Katayama,T., Proc. of 31st Int.SAMPE Symp., 1986, pp.1666-73
- 5) Hirai,T., Hamada,H. and Yokoyama,A., J. of Society of Material Science, Japan, 1984, 33, 364, pp.55-60.